

1 **Climate threats on growth of rear-edge European beech peripheral populations in**
2 **Spain**

3 **I. Dorado-Liñán^{1,2*}, L. Akhmetzyanov^{2,3}, A. Menzel^{2,4}**

4
5 ¹ *Forest Research Centre, Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y*
6 *Alimentaria (INIA-CIFOR), Madrid, Spain*

7 ² *Ecoclimatology, Technische Universität München, Freising, Germany*

8 ³ *Forest Ecology and Forest Management Group, Wageningen University, Wageningen,*
9 *the Netherlands*

10 ⁴ *Institute for Advanced Study, Technische Universität München, Garching, Germany*

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12 (*) Corresponding author

13

14 **Abstract**

15 European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) forests in the Iberian Peninsula are a clear example
16 of a temperate forest tree species at the rear edge of its large distribution area in Europe.
17 The expected drier and warmer climate may alter tree growth and species distribution.
18 Consequently, the peripheral populations will most likely be the most threatened ones.
19 Four peripheral beech forests in the Iberian Peninsula were studied in order to assess
20 the climate factors influencing tree growth for the last six decades. The analyses
21 included an individual tree approach in order to detect not only the changes in the
22 sensitivity to climate, but also the potential size-mediated sensitivity to climate. Our
23 results revealed a dominant influence of previous and current year summer on tree
24 growth during the last six decades, although the analysis in two equally-long periods
25 unveiled changes and shifts in tree sensitivity to climate. The individual tree approach
26 showed that those changes in tree response to climate are not size dependent in most
27 of the cases. We observed a reduced negative effect of warmer winter temperatures at
28 some sites and a generalized increased influence of previous year climatic conditions
29 on current year tree growth. These results highlight the crucial role played by
30 carryover effects and stored carbohydrates for future tree growth and species
31 persistence.

32 **Keywords:** *European beech; tree growth; peripheral populations, rear edge; climate*
33 *change.*

34 **Introduction**

35

36 Climate is the main factor responsible for shaping plant species' distribution and
37 communities worldwide (Woodward 1987). Any change in climate bears implications on
38 growth and persistence for a given plant species, and selection pressure generally
39 increases towards the edges of the geographical distribution area (Hampe and Petit 2005).
40 Populations at the edges of their natural distribution mostly occur in regions that have
41 provided suitable conditions for the species' occurrence in the past, however, their current
42 status of marginality turns growth limiting factors close to the maximum (minimum)
43 values of the species tolerance (Parmesan 1996). The study of the dynamics of those
44 populations at the margins has gained increasing interest, especially of the ones located
45 at the so-called "rear edge". The rear edge, equatorial edge or retreating edge is defined
46 as the low-latitude margins of a species' distribution where plant growth is mostly
47 constrained by high temperatures and/or water scarcity (Hampe and Petit 2005). The
48 response of rear-edge populations to water deficit may help to estimate tolerance limits
49 and adaptation of species to forthcoming climate change. In this context, trees are
50 valuable resources to study adaptation to climate change at their margins, since their
51 resilience makes them persisting long after the climate becomes challenging for them (La
52 Marche 1973). Many rear-edge forests face year-to-year harsh growing conditions
53 intensified by spontaneous drought events (Beniston et al. 2007; Christensen et al. 2007;
54 Briffa et al. 2009) producing related growth declines, loss of productivity and even
55 mortality events (Allen et al. 2010; Ciais et al. 2005; Galiano et al. 2010; Jump et al. 2006;
56 Linares et al. 2011). Given drought sensitivity and temperature-induced stress of water-
57 limited populations, drought-prone forests will likely become more important in a global
58 warming scenario. Reduced wood formation is one of the first impacts of drought and
59 occurs before visual symptoms of decline and tree death appear. Thus,
60 dendrochronological analyses show up as useful approach to investigate the ecological
61 implications of climate-driven changes on forest dynamics and to forecast tree decline.

62 The Mediterranean basin (MB) represents a major transitional zone in Europe, where
63 several boreal and temperate species meet their rear distribution edges. Climatic records
64 have shown a significant increase in the number of warm days (Andrade et al. 2012;
65 Moberg et al. 2006) and heat waves (Della-Marta et al. 2007, Perkins et al. 2012) over

66 the last several decades for whole Europe. However, only the MB shows a significant
67 increase in dryness (Hartmann et al. 2013; Sousa et al. 2011; Hoerling et al. 2012) which
68 also seems to be unprecedented in the context of the last centuries (Luterbacher et al.
69 2004, 2006). Furthermore, several regional and global models have consistently predicted
70 increased drought impacts and heat waves in the MB in the subsequent decades (Giorgi
71 and Lionello 2008; Mariotti 2010), which could either produce an upward migration of
72 plant species or convert mountains into dead-end streets for many rear-edge populations
73 (Gates 1993).

74 European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) is a clear example of a temperate tree species
75 meeting the rear edge of a large distribution area in the MB, where forests display lower
76 rates of growth and production compared with trees at the non-distribution limits (Jump
77 et al. 2006). Concretely, in the Iberian Peninsula (IP hereafter) there are several peripheral
78 European beech forests growing in climatically stressed areas at the rear edges of the
79 species' natural distribution (Aranda et al. 2000; Peñuelas et al. 2007) that may serve as
80 suitable experimental sites. Some pioneer studies on European beech. in the IP showed
81 that beech growth at its southern limit is strongly limited by drought and is being
82 progressively replaced by Mediterranean holm oak forests at the lowest altitudinal range
83 (Peñuelas et al. 2007).

84 The decrease in future distribution area of beech forests is predicted by various
85 bioclimatic models (Thuiller et al. 2005; Czúcz et al. 2011). Species distribution models
86 also report a future retreat of beech to higher altitudes (Zimmermann et al. 2009) and
87 latitudes (Falk and Hempelmann 2013), while dynamic forests models suggest that beech
88 could remain at lower altitudes as far as summer precipitation does not dramatically
89 decrease (Bugmann and Pfister 2000; Rasche et al. 2012). Considering that European
90 beech requires high levels of atmospheric humidity due to a low tolerance to summer
91 drought (Gessler et al. 2007; Lebourgeois et al. 2005), future projected increases in
92 summer drought and annual temperature may lead to die-off of beech forests at local
93 scales and / or shifting to higher altitudes.

94 Studies on tree response to climate in the interface of survival are needed to assess the
95 potential consequences of further warming and increasing drought stress on temperate
96 and boreal tree species. Thus, the selection of sites at rear edges and at the dry limit of the
97 species' distribution (generally being this limit the lowest altitudinal and/or latitudinal
98 locations) is important when working on drought effects since summer drought will be
99 one of the main drivers of tree-growth (Hampe and Petit 2005).

100 In order to contribute to the body of knowledge on the response of temperate tree species
101 at the dry limits, we study four peripheral European beech forests located on the IP. The
102 main aim is to identify current and future climatic threats potentially challenging the
103 persistence and survival of these valuable forests. Three out of the four sites were
104 unexplored in terms of tree growth information and relationship with climate, thus the
105 present study is the first assessment of the climate-growth relationships at these marginal
106 forests. Furthermore, we tackle the forest response to changing climatic conditions from
107 the individual tree's perspective (Carrer 2011; Dorado Liñán et al. 2012; Rozas 2015) to
108 evaluate the potential size-related sensitivity to climate in each population. We
109 hypothesize that tree-growth at the four peripheral beech populations will be mainly
110 constrained by summer climate and that such a response might be size-dependent.

111 **Materials and methods**

112 **Study sites**

113

114 The study was carried out at four natural European beech forests located on the IP (see
115 Table 1 for detailed information). The four sites host peripheral populations at the rear
116 edge of their natural distribution range in Europe, facing warmer and drier conditions.
117 Two of the sites are located in the center of the IP, 100 km apart from each other: Hayedo
118 de Montejo de la Sierra (MON) in the province of Madrid; and Natural Park of Tejera
119 Negra (TJN) in the Guadalajara province (Fig. 1). The other two European beech forests
120 are located in the North-East of Spain facing the Mediterranean Sea: one is the beech
121 forest in Turó de l'Home (TDH) in the Parc Natural del Montseny close to Barcelona;
122 and the second one is known as Tancades beech forest (TAN) in Parc Natural dels Ports
123 located 200 km south of Barcelona.

124

125 The TJN forest is located at the north-east of Guadalajara province at 1500 m a.s.l. The
126 soil is relatively poor associated with steep slopes that limit to a great extent tree growth.
127 The sampling was carried out on the southern slope of the massif consisting mainly of
128 quartzite and slate (Pardo et al. 2004), hosting a natural mono-specific beech forest with
129 no visible regeneration. Trees at this site are sprouts from logging that was a common
130 practice in the past in central Iberian Peninsula; however there is no specific historical
131 information available on other potential use and exploitation in this forest. Some isolated
132 individuals are older, probably kept for seed production.

Study site	Acronym	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Coordinates	Number of trees/ cores	Diameter of trees (cm)	Age of trees (years)	Reliable time span	BAI (mm ² year ⁻¹) reliable period	BAI (mm ² year ⁻¹) 1950-2012	Grid cell E-Obs	
										Longitude	Latitude
Natural Park of Tejera Negra	TJN	1580	3.37°W; 41.24°N	22/33	54.6±42.8	84.9±21.7	1900-2012	2200.9±1261.4	2569.4±1086.4	3-3.5°W	41-41.5°N
Hayedo de Montejo de la Sierra	MON	1250	3.49°W; 41.10°N	19/34	70.0±22.2	139.0±50.5	1835-2012	2852.7±751.1	2619.9±693.5	3-3.5°W	41-41.5°N
Turó de l'Home (PN Montseny)	TDH	1310	2.45°E; 41.76°N	22/29	34.3±8.1	80.1±10.4	1929-2012	1012.1±434.7	1239.8±280.4	2-2.5°E	41.5- 42°N
Fagedes Tancades (PN Els Ports)	TAN	1180	0.29°E; 40.76°N	20/33	56.5±17.5	99.5±32.1	1734-2012	2349.5±618.1	2515.6±624.3	0-0.5°E	40.5-41°N

133

134 **Table 1.** Main geographical characteristics of each study site, number of trees and cores
135 for each chronology, mean ± standard deviation in diameter and age of trees, reliable
136 (EPS>0.85) time span, mean basal area increment (BAI) and standard deviation for the
137 reliable period, and for the common period of analysis 1950-2012. The coordinates of
138 the grid cell of E-OBS defined for each sampling site are also provided.

139

140

141 MON is a natural beech-oak forest located close to TJN, at the so-called Sistema Central of the
142 IP between 1250-1500 m a.s.l. The soil is a humic cambisol (Pardo et al. 1997) and the forest
143 is dominated by *Quercus pyrenaica* Willd. (sub-Mediterranean forest). The forest has
144 historically been used to obtain firewood and as a resting place for livestock (Gil et al. 2010).
145 Pruning was a common practice until the beginning of the 1960s, when cattle management and
146 pruning were forbidden in the forest, although the protection of the area was effective only since
147 1974 (Pardo 2000). Nowadays, it is a biosphere reserve where human intervention is very
148 limited. The individuals of European beech are mainly centenary trees.

149

150 *Figure 1. Distribution map of Fagus sylvatica in Europe with the location of the four*
 151 *sampling sites. Bottom panel display the monthly variations in precipitation and*
 152 *temperature as anomalies respect to the period 1950-2012 derived from E-OBS. Mean*
 153 *annual temperature (MAT) and total annual precipitation (MAP) are also provided. Note*
 154 *that TJN and MON are located in the same grid cell.*

155

156 The climate at MON and TJN is similar due to the proximity to each other (Fig. 1). It is
 157 continental with low temperatures during winter and a hot summer concurring with the
 158 period of the lowest rainfall. Precipitation mainly occurs during the late spring and
 159 autumn months. According to different sources of climate (Hijmans et al. 2005; Gil et al.
 160 2010) TJN is cooler (annual mean temperature 7.2°C) and wetter (annual sum of
 161 precipitation 900mm) than MON (9.4°C and 800mm).

162

163 TDH is located at 50 km north-west of Barcelona where beech forests occur above the
 164 typical Mediterranean holm oak forest (*Quercus ilex* L.) that dominates the lower
 165 elevations (Bolós 1983). European beech at TDH grows on dystric regosols and
 166 cambisols established over schist and granodiorite lithology (Jump et al. 2006). Forest
 167 have been historically managed by removing selected trees, however the management

168 pressure was supposedly not severe. The sampling site located at 1300 m a.s.l. is a pure
169 beech forest located on a steep southern slope, where no signs of current human
170 disturbances are present. According to the climatogram based on E-OBS data (Haylock
171 et al. 2008), the hottest months in TDH are July and August. TDH is the rainiest among
172 all four sites with a mean annual sum of precipitation of 950mm (Hijmans et al. 2005). The
173 highest precipitation occurs in autumn, and the driest month is July followed by the winter
174 months of January and February.

175

176 TAN is located south of TDH, close to the Mediterranean coast. TAN hosts one of the
177 most meridional European beech populations in Europe which grows at 1180 m. a.s.l. on
178 a very steep slope as open forest with inclusion of some European yew trees. Since most
179 of the beech forest is a private property, there is no information on the past forest
180 management. However the scars and sprouts of the branches evidence that pruning was a
181 common practice in the past, most likely for firewood. The steep topography makes
182 climate highly influenced by altitude and aspect: on lower altitudes the climate is
183 Mediterranean with typical holm oak forests and as the altitude increases, climate changes
184 to sub-Mediterranean with higher precipitation and lower temperatures and the forests are
185 dominated by *Pinus sylvestris* L. Climate at TAN is the most Mediterranean of all four
186 sites, and shows a mean annual precipitation of 750mm with a maximum of rain in autumn.
187 The highest temperatures are registered in July and August concurring with the driest
188 months.

189

190 **Sampling, measurement and chronologies development**

191

192 The target species, European beech, is characterized for being more shade tolerant but
193 less drought tolerant than other widely distributed broadleaf temperate tree species such
194 as *Quercus petraea* (Mattuschka) Liebl. (Lendzion and Leuschner 2008). The longevity
195 of the species in the Mediterranean basin ranges between 200-600 years and seems to be
196 related to the growth rate (Di Filippo et al. 2015).

197

198 A total of 83 European beech trees were cored at all four sites during spring of 2013. Two
199 cores per tree were taken at 1.3 m height from healthy-dominant trees using an increment
200 borer of 40 cm in length and 5 mm of diameter. The cores were then labeled, air-dried
201 and sanded with progressively finer grades of sandpaper until the tree-ring structure was
202 clearly visible under the stereo microscope. Standard dendroclimatic procedures were

203 applied to each site's collection of cores. Samples of each site were visually crossdated
204 following Stokes and Smiley (1968) and ring-widths measured with an accuracy of 0.01mm
205 using a Lintab 6 (RINNTECH) measuring device. Ring-width series were checked for
206 possible dating errors using the computer software COFECHA (Holmes, 1983).

207

208 The diameters at the breast height (DBH) measured in the field were used to convert each
209 individual ring-width series to basal area increment (BAI) using dplR (Bunn 2008). The
210 chronologies were computed as bi-weight robust mean to reduce the bias caused by extreme
211 values and an autoregressive model was applied to remove the autocorrelation of the series
212 (Cook and Kairiukstis 1990). The statistical quality of each chronology was checked via
213 Expressed Population Signal (EPS; Wigley et al. 1984). A threshold value of $EPS > 0.85$ was
214 used to determine the cutoff year of the time-span that could be considered reliable. The
215 common period 1950-2012 was used for further analyses in order to avoid the period of
216 intensive logging in TJN (see also Fig. 2).

217

218 For the individual-tree analysis, a high-pass filter consisting on a 10-years spline was fitted to
219 every BAI series in order to remove individual non-climatic signals (i.e., pests, competition,
220 microsite conditions) which are usually minimized when building the mean site chronology.

221

222 **Climate data and analysis**

223

224 In order to have a homogenous source of climate data for all sites, the high-resolution and
225 homogenized gridded data of daily climate over Europe (E-OBS; Haylock et al. 2008) was
226 chosen as input climate data. E-OBS is based on the largest available pan-European data set of
227 instrumental stations and represent an improvement respect to other existing gridded climate
228 data. Monthly temperature means and precipitation totals were downloaded for the $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$
229 grid-cell around every sampled stand. Similarly, the Standardized Precipitation-
230 Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI; Vicente-Serrano et al. 2010) which is a multiscalar drought
231 index was also used to assess the sensitivity of the tree-ring series to moisture deficit. The 1-
232 months SPEI data was obtained for the same grid-cells than the E-OBS temperature and
233 precipitation data.

234

235

236 *Figure 2. Basal area increment (BAI) chronologies from TJN, MON, TDH and TAN. Dashed*
 237 *red lines mark the beginning of the reliable period (EPS>0.85) and blue lines delimit the*
 238 *common period used for further analyses (1950-2012).*

239

240 The influence of climate on tree growth was investigated for the time-span 1950-2012 in order
 241 to omit the period of intensive management in some forests (i.e., TJN). The influence of climate
 242 on BAI during the last six decades was tested by computing Pearson correlations with monthly
 243 climate variables. Bootstrapped significance levels were assessed using R-package ‘boot’
 244 (Canty and Ripley 2016). Furthermore, in order to check for potential changes in the forests’
 245 sensitivity to climate, Spearman rank correlations were computed between BAI chronologies
 246 and monthly as well as seasonal climate variables in two comparably long periods (1950-1981
 247 and 1982-2012) from April of the previous year to October of the year of tree-ring formation.
 248 A non-parametric test was chosen due to the limited length of the two segments. The potential
 249 type error I associated to multiple testing was minimized by using a minimum significance level
 250 of 0.03. This analysis enabled identifying the limiting factors and seasons for tree growth at
 251 each of the studied sites and allowed detecting changes in the sensitivity to climate.

252

253 The changes in the trees' sensitivity to the seasonal climate variables detected in the previous
254 analysis and the potential size-dependent response to climate were further tested using an
255 individual-tree approach (Carrer 2011; Dorado Liñán et al. 2012). For that, each single
256 individual BAI series was correlated with the main seasonal climate drivers during each
257 subperiod identified in the previous step. The results of the individual correlations are shown
258 as asymmetric beanplots (Kampstra 2008) which allow the comparison of the average of the
259 correlations, the individual observations and the estimated density of the distributions of the
260 individual observations. The differences in the distribution of the individual series correlation
261 with the seasonal climate were tested using the paired Kolmogórov-Smirnov test (KS).

262 The statistical dependence between tree size (DBH) and sensitivity to the selected seasonal
263 climate variable was also explored by using a Spearman rank correlation. For the earlier period
264 (1950-1981) the actual size of the tree at that time was calculated by subtracting the
265 accumulated growth from 1982 until 2012 from the DBH measured during the field campaign.
266 As a last step and in order to better visualize the timing of the growth-climate changes over
267 time, the four BAI chronologies were correlated with the seasonal climate factors by means of
268 a 31-yrs centered moving correlation and the results plotted using a modified version of the
269 butterfly moving correlation plot (Salzer et al. 2014). All analyses were done using R software
270 version 3.2.3 (R Core Team, 2015).

271

272 **Results**

273

274 **Characteristics and growth of the peripheral beech populations**

275

276 MON forest hosts older and bigger individuals with a mean tree age of 139 years and 70
277 cm of DBH on average, whereas TDH is the youngest forests with a mean age of 80 years
278 and individuals 34 cm of DBH on average (Table 1). MON is also the forest displaying
279 the largest standard deviation in individual age but not in size. TJN displayed the largest
280 range in size.

281

282 The BAI chronology from TJN had a total length of 138 years and the reliable chronology
283 spanned from 1900 to 2012. TJN was one of the sites with clearer signs of perturbations
284 such as the sharp increase in BAI around 1940. Since then, BAI has considerably
285 decreased and the variability has been reduced (Table 1).

286

287 The trees from MON provided the longest chronology among the four sites: from 1750
288 until 2012 (Fig. 2). The statistically reliable period (EPS>0.85 threshold) started in 1835
289 but showed increasing BAI and inflated variance until 1890. Since then, the variations in
290 BAI were more homogeneous until nowadays. Despite this, MON was still the forest
291 displaying the largest productivity on average (circa 2620 mm²/year) for the common
292 period of analysis 1950-2012.

293

294 The BAI chronology from TDH was the shortest and covered the period from 1919 until
295 2012 being reliable from 1929 onwards. The trees at TDH displayed the lowest productivity
296 during the last six decades (Table 1) and lower interannual variability (Fig. 2) compared to
297 the other three sites.

298

299 The BAI chronology from TAN began on 1844, though the reliable period started in 1873.
300 The productivity during the last 130 years has not largely changed and the BAI for the
301 last 62 years (2516 mm²/year) was similar to that from the reliable period (2350
302 mm²/year). Moreover, the productivity of the last decades is very similar to that of MON.

303 **Climatic drivers of tree growth**

304 All four BAI chronologies generally revealed a poor climate sensitivity for the last 63
305 years, displaying significant correlations mainly with summer months, either from the
306 current and / or previous year of growth (Fig. 3). MON was the site displaying the highest
307 sensitivity to climate, whereas TAN appeared as the least sensitive. The amount of
308 significant correlations revealed temperature as the climate factor exerting a prevailing
309 influence on tree growth at all study sites for the common period 1950-2012. However,
310 Spearman rank correlations between the BAI chronologies and climate in the two sub
311 periods 1950-1981 and 1982-2012 (Fig. 4) evidenced changes in the trees' sensitivity to
312 climate during the last decades.

313

314 TJN displayed a low number of correlations with monthly climate variables but several
315 significant correlations with seasonal (summer) precipitation and SPEI from previous and
316 current year of growth (Fig. 4). During the earlier period 1950-1981, tree growth at TJN
317 was influenced by current year June-July precipitation ($r_s=0.43$; $p<0.03$) and June-July
318 SPEI ($r_s=0.48$; $p<0.01$), whereas for the later period, 1982-2012 the significant seasonal
319 correlations were found with previous year summer: June-August precipitation ($r_s=0.42$;
320 $p<0.03$) and June-July SPEI ($r_s=0.43$; $p<0.03$). The only significant relationship with

321 temperature observed was the negative correlation with previous year August temperature
 322 during the earlier period 1950-1981 ($r_s=-0.43$; $p<0.03$).

323
 324

325 **Figure 3.** Correlations of the site BAI chronologies with monthly temperature (T),
 326 precipitation (P) and drought (SPEI) from April of the previous year (upper case letters)
 327 to October of the current year (low-case letters). Shaded areas highlight summer season.
 328 Dashed and pointed lines indicate 95% and 99% bootstrapped significance levels,
 329 respectively.

330

331 Similarly to TJN, MON also displayed significant monthly and seasonal correlations with
 332 current (previous) year spring and summer precipitation and SPEI in the 1950-1981
 333 (1982-2012) period (Fig. 4). During the earlier period, the BAI chronology from MON
 334 showed significant positive correlations with current year spring-early summer
 335 precipitation ($r_s=0.42$; $p<0.03$) and SPEI ($r_s=0.42$; $p<0.03$) as well as negative

336 correlations with winter temperature (Jan-Feb, $r_s=-0.48$; $p<0.01$). During the later period,
337 the correlation with previous year precipitation and SPEI and Jan-Feb temperature
338 became non-significant, whereas the correlation with previous year summer precipitation
339 and SPEI turned significant ($r_s=0.46$ and $r_s=0.45$; $p<0.03$, respectively).

340

341 Tree growth at TDH showed a poor relation with climate variables climate in the two
342 subperiods. No significant correlations with seasonal climate variables for the current
343 and/or previous year of growth were found for any of the two subperiods (Fig. 4). The
344 only significant correlations with single months were found during the earlier period
345 1950-1982, whereas no significant correlation was found for the later period. The
346 influence of the current year summer season on tree growth during the earlier period could
347 also be observed in the significant correlation with July precipitation and SPEI ($r_s=0.42$
348 and $r_s=0.40$, $p<0.03$; respectively) while the only significant temperature relationship was
349 found with previous year December ($r_s=0.46$).

350

351 TAN forest appeared as the least sensitive to climate when performing correlations for
352 the full period of study (1950-2012). However, the correlation analysis in the two
353 subperiods revealed a significant influence of current year spring to summer temperature
354 and SPEI ($r_s=0.43$ and $r_s=-0.44$; $p<0.03$, respectively) during the earlier period. During
355 the later period, the positive correlation with spring-summer temperature and the negative
356 with spring-summer SPEI became non-significant and tree growth displayed stronger
357 correlations with current year spring-summer precipitation ($r_s=0.51$; $p<0.01$).

358

359 **Individual-tree response to climate**

360

361 The individual trees' correlation with the significant seasonal climate variables (monthly
362 climate variables in the case of TDH) identified in Fig. 4 allowed the visualization of the
363 changes in the sensitivity to climate at individual and population level (Fig. 5; for detailed
364 monthly correlations, readers are referred to Supplementary Fig. 1).

365

366

367

368 **Figure 4.** Spearman rank correlation of the BAI chronologies with monthly temperature

369 (*T*), precipitation (*P*) and drought (SPEI) from April of the previous year (upper case) to

370 October of the current year (low-case letters) for the two periods: 1950-1981 and 1982-

371 2012. The most representative season (or month) is shown at the end. Dashed and pointed

372 lines indicate 97% and 99% significance levels, respectively.

373

374 According to the results of the Kolmogórov-Smirnov paired test, TJN displayed

375 significant variations ($p < 0.001$) in the sensitivity to current year June-July precipitation

376 and SPEI between the two subperiods, changing from positive to non-significant. In turn,

377 no significant changes were observed in the sensitivity to previous year summer

378 precipitation and SPEI. However, the negative correlation with previous year August
 379 temperature showed a significant change in sensitivity of the individual trees that became
 380 less negative during the latter period. The significant changes in sensitivity to current year
 381 summer precipitation and SPEI were linked to a modification of the individual trees'
 382 correlation distribution that changed from unimodal to bimodal pattern.

383

384 Similarly, the other continental site MON also showed significant changes in the
 385 individual trees' response to climate to the current year seasonal variables (January-
 386 February temperature, April-July SPEI) but not for the previous year seasons (June-July
 387 precipitation and SPEI) (Fig. 5). The negative correlations with January-February
 388 temperatures of the earlier period 1950-1981 became mainly positive during the latter
 389 period 1982-2012, whereas the positive correlation of the individual trees with April to
 390 July SPEI became less positive. The correlations with previous year summer precipitation
 391 and SPEI remained positive as well as the positive correlation with current year spring to
 392 summer precipitation.

393

394

395 *Figure 5. Asymmetric beanplots showing the Spearman rank correlation of every*
 396 *individual BAI series with the most limiting climate season / month of temperature,*
 397 *precipitation and SPEI defined in Fig. 4 for the periods 1950-1981 and 1982-2012. (*)*
 398 *indicates significant differences ($p < 0.001$) between the two periods according to the*
 399 *Kolmogórov-Smirnov paired test. Dashed lines indicate 97% significance level.*

400 In contrast, trees from TDH displayed significant changes in the individual response to
401 previous year December temperature, whereas non-significant differences between the
402 individual-tree positive correlations with current year July precipitation and SPEI were
403 found between the subperiods 1950-1981 and 1982-2012. The negative influence of
404 previous year December became less negative during 1982-2012.

405

406 TAN displayed significant changes in the individual trees' sensitivity for all seasonal
407 climate variables identified: current year May to September temperature and SPEI, and
408 current year April to October precipitation. During the period 1950-1981, individual trees
409 displayed positive correlations with current year May-September temperature and SPEI,
410 while during the later period the individual correlations became less positive. In line with
411 that, the correlations values between individual trees and May to August precipitation of
412 the current year changed from negative to positive correlations.

413

414 The relationship between the individual correlation with the climatic seasons of Fig. 4
415 and the DBH (Supplementary Fig. 2) revealed a general lack of association between the
416 sensitivity to the climatic season and the size of the tree. Only three coefficients out of 32
417 were significant ($p < 0.01$) and the three of them were related to tree growth and summer
418 hydroclimate in the central Iberian Peninsula sites. More specifically, a significant
419 climate-size relationship was only found between the individual trees from TJN and
420 current year June-July precipitation and SPEI during the period 1982-2012 ($r_s = -0.56$ and
421 $r_s = -0.55$, respectively) and previous year June-September precipitation in MON ($r_s = -$
422 0.59) during the earlier period. No significant relationships were found between
423 temperature sensitivities and tree-size.

424

425 **Changes in the BAI chronologies response to climate**

426

427 The moving Pearson correlations between the four BAI chronologies and the seasonal
428 climate represented as modified butterfly plots illustrates the timing of the changes in the
429 sensitivity to current and previous year climate (Fig. 6). TJN displayed a general loss of
430 trees' sensitivity to current year summer hydroclimate (June-July precipitation and SPEI)
431 and increasing influence of previous year summer hydroclimate (June-July precipitation
432 and SPEI) that became significant in recent times. Similarly, MON also displayed an
433 increasing influence of previous year summer hydroclimate that became significant
434 during 1980s (Fig. 6). In turn, the negative effect on tree growth of current year January-

435 February temperatures changed into non-significant around 1970, whereas the influence
 436 of current year spring-summer precipitation and SPEI became non-significant at the
 437 beginning of 1980s.

438
 439

440 **Figure 6.** Temporal evolution in the climate-growth relationships at TJN, MON, TDH
 441 and TAN. Each panel shows the moving correlations of the corresponding BAI
 442 chronology the seasonal temperature (red), precipitation (blue) and SPEI (orange)
 443 defined in Fig. 4 and shown as butterfly correlation plots. The original color represents
 444 the real sign of the correlation and the smoothed color is a mirror for a better
 445 visualization of the changes. Dashed lines indicate 95% significance level.

446

447 TDH displayed a negative correlation with previous year December temperature that
 448 became non-significant at the beginning of 1970s. The positive correlation with current
 449 year July precipitation and SPEI was continuously significant between mid 1970s and
 450 mid 1980s.

451 Trees from TAN showed a marked shift in the sensitivity to current year climate,
452 particularly to April to October precipitation and March to August SPEI (Fig. 6). The
453 relationship with both seasons changed from negative to positive. The inflexion point
454 around 1980s was concurrent with the loss of the significant positive relationship with
455 current year May-September temperature.

456 **Discussion**

457
458 Tree growth at the four peripheral populations under study has mainly been
459 constrained by summer climate conditions during the last six decades (see Fig. 3),
460 although some of the sites seemed to display a poor climate sensitivity (i.e., TAN).
461 This significant negative impact of summer temperature on tree growth in TJN, MON
462 and TDH has been also described for forests located at the Italian pre-Alps (Piutti and
463 Cescatti 1997; Di Filippo et al. 2007), Mediterranean mountains (Gutierrez 1988) and
464 also for beech forests growing under Atlantic climate in Spain and in Central Europe
465 (Lebourgeois et al. 2005; Cailleret and Hendrik 2011). Therefore, the negative effect
466 of summer temperature seems to be a common limiting factor for beech growth not
467 only at the peripheral populations. Similarly, the positive effect of precipitation in
468 early summer in TJN, MON and TDH pointed to certain moisture-limitations at those
469 sites. These results are somehow expected at the southernmost limit of the species
470 distribution. The lack of precipitation during summer combined with the negative
471 impact on summer temperatures may inhibit photosynthesis, transpiration and cell
472 development in beech due to rapid stomata closure as a response of trees to drought
473 (Aranda et. al 2000; Epron and Dreyer 1990; Rozas 2001).

474
475 However, the correlation with climate in the two subperiods (see Fig. 4) unveiled
476 consistent changes in sensitivity to climate during the last six decades in most of the
477 four peripheral beech populations under investigation. Thus, climate-growth
478 relationships described in Fig. 3 for the common period of analysis 1950-2012 have
479 not been stable along the last six decades, and significant changes in the sensitivity to
480 climate occurred. In fact, the absence of significant correlations with climate observed
481 in beech trees of TAN in Fig. 3 is not due to a general lack of climate sensitivity but
482 to a shift in the climate response.

483

484 Furthermore, in contrast to our hypothesis, the individual-tree approach revealed that
485 the sensitivity to climate was generally not size-related. Our finding contradicts
486 Mérian and Lebourgeois (2011) who found significant difference in climate sensitivity
487 of beech trees across size classes. According to their results, larger (dominant) trees
488 were more sensitive to summer droughts than smaller (suppressed) ones. We only
489 found significant size-mediated sensitivity to summer hydroclimate in TJN for the
490 later period and in MON for the earlier period. However, we cannot conclude that
491 older trees were displaying higher sensitivities to summer hydroclimate than younger
492 ones, in fact in MON the opposite was true. It should be noted that, in contrast with
493 our study that only considered dominant or codominant trees, the diameter groups
494 defined by Mérian and Lebourgeois (2011) were based on canopy position, thus
495 including the effect of competition which also influences the individual tree
496 sensitivity to climate (Rozas 2015).

497

498 *Enhanced lagged-effects*

499

500 The response to climate of the four peripheral forests was not homogeneous across
501 sites and has not been uniform over time. However, we could identify three relevant
502 changes: the increasing dependency on previous year climate (TJN and MON), the
503 reduction of the negative effect of winter temperatures (MON and TDH) and the
504 marked shift in the climate response of TAN.

505

506 The two peripheral populations located at the central Iberian Peninsula TJN and MON
507 showed increasing correlations with previous year summer hydroclimate
508 (precipitation and SPEI) that became significant since 1980s and 1990s for MON and
509 TJN, respectively. This evidences an increasing limitation of tree growth by previous
510 year summer drought, whereas the sensitivity to current year growth hydroclimate has
511 decreased and become non-significant during the last decades at both sites. A larger
512 sensitivity of beech populations to previous year than current year summer climate has
513 been described across the distribution range (Cavin and Jump 2017) and close to the
514 equatorial edge (Rozas 2001). Lagged effects are particularly common in deciduous
515 species since the onset of the growing season relies on the existing carbon pool to
516 sustain leaf formation (Barbaroux et al. 2002; Scartazza et al. 2013). Furthermore,
517 lag-effects are enhanced as a consequence of drought-induced stomata closure that
518 lowers the carbon gain (Cochard et al. 2001; Breda et al. 2006), and beech trees in

519 MON have been described to close stomata and reduce photosynthetic activity due to
520 summer drought (Aranda et al. 2000). Other authors suggested that lagged climate
521 signals in tree ring chronologies from masting tree species may also be induced by the
522 growth reduction associated with mast years (Hackett-Pain et al. 2015). Regardless of
523 the reason for the observed enhancement of the lag-effects of TJN and MON trees
524 (either increasing climate constrains, trade-off between growth and seed production,
525 or a combinations of both) this may have important implications for the tree carbon
526 storage and hence, tree growth and survival (McDowell et al., 2008).

527

528 *The role of winter temperature*

529

530 The results of two sites (MON and TDH) also showed a reduction of the negative
531 effects of winter temperatures on tree growth, which may also have implications for
532 the tree carbon storage. Higher temperatures during winter are known to reduce the
533 amount of carbohydrates needed to recover from freeze-thaw-induced xylem
534 embolism (Sperry and Sullivan 1992; Cochard et al. 2001; Sala et al. 2012). In fact,
535 the January-February temperatures in MON have significantly increased during the
536 last six decades (see Supplementary Fig. 3). On the other hand, temperatures over zero
537 during winter have been described to enhance respiration and carbohydrates
538 consumption (Scartazza et al. 2013; Simard et al. 2013). Considering that summer and
539 winter temperatures are expected to rise in the next decades in the MB (IPCC, 2013),
540 adaptation and survival of beech trees in MON and TDH may depend not only on the
541 effect of water scarcity and/or high temperatures during summer (that limit
542 photosynthetic activity), but most likely also on winter temperatures. Warmer
543 temperatures during winter may enhance tissue respiration rates leading to losses in
544 stored carbon, which combined with water stress during summer may contribute in a
545 long term to drought-induced mortality due to carbon starvation (Allen et al. 2010;
546 McDowell et al. 2011).

547

548 *Shifts in the sensitivity to climate*

549

550 Interestingly, TAN showed a clear shift in the response to climate between the mid-
551 1970s and the beginning of the 1980s. Late spring-to-summer temperature exerted a
552 positive impact on tree growth and the correlation with March-August SPEI was
553 negative, pointing to a non-moisture limited site. However, since the end of 1970s and

554 beginning of 1980s, tree growth was no longer positively associated with late spring-
555 to-summer temperature but to April-October precipitation, whereas the positive
556 influence of temperature disappeared, revealing that TAN is no longer a non-moisture
557 limited site. Such a change is concurrent with a significant increase in May to
558 September mean temperatures, particularly evident since 1980s (see Supplementary
559 Fig. 3)

560 Shifts in sensitivity to climate such as the one observed in TAN have been widely
561 reported at leading edges of species distributions (D'Arrigo et al. 2008 and references
562 therein). The potential non-climate related causes such as age-related effects (Carrer
563 and Urbinati 2004) and uncertainties in climate data and statistical processes (Esper
564 et al. 2009) have been also largely discussed. However, at the rear edges the
565 information is scarcer and less conclusive (Hampe and Petit 2005). Among the
566 potential causes of such shifts in sensitivity to climate is the so-called 1980s regime
567 shift (Reid et al. 2016). Such an alteration is described as a major and global
568 biophysical shift attributed to changes in temperature, aerosols, their interactions with
569 clouds and the increase in sunshine durations since 1980s. Those changes seemed to
570 have locally enhanced drought impacts on tree growth at the Iberian Peninsula
571 (Büntgen et al. 2013) due to the increase in temperatures since the 1970s (Brunet et
572 al. 2007) and the upward trend in sunshine duration and surface solar radiation since
573 1980 (Sanchez Lorenzo et al. 2007, 2013), particularly pronounced during spring and
574 summer. Although the seasonal precipitation record does not display a significant
575 decreasing trend, May to September mean temperatures do show a significant
576 increasing trend, particularly evident since the 1980s (Supplementary Fig. 3) and this
577 could cause a shift in sensitivity.

578

579 On the other hand, TAN forest has not been always a protected forest and a reduction
580 on habitat modification pressure during the recent decades should be taken into
581 consideration as a potential cause (Linares et al. 2011). In fact, the cessation of the
582 logging activity is known to lead to a forest densification and enhanced competition
583 for resources (Linares et al. 2010; Gómez-Aparicio et al. 2011) such as water during
584 the growing season. However, disentangling climate-induced tree responses to climate
585 from those caused by land-used changes is challenging in forests historically
586 managed.

587 For instances, the response to climate of the TDH beech forest has been extensively
588 studied (Gutiérrez 1988; Peñuelas and Boada 2003; Jump et al. 2006; Peñuelas et al.

589 2007, 2008) and most of those studies related the tree decline to increasingly drier
590 conditions (Jump et al. 2006) and upslope migrations that could be due to climate
591 change, land use-changes or both (Peñuelas and Boada 2003; Peñuelas et al. 2008).
592 However, we did not find a response at TDH that may indicate that drought is being
593 the limiting factor for tree growth and the main cause of the observed reduced growth
594 rate during the last decades.

595 **Conclusions**

596 Our results evidence the site-specific nature of climate growth relationships of peripheral
597 populations previously described by other authors (Cavin and Jump 2017). The four
598 European beech populations considered in our study are characterized by different levels
599 of environmental dryness and consequently show different levels of adaptation to
600 drought. However, the characterization of the influence of climate on tree growth in two
601 subperiods revealed consistent changes during the last decades. The two continental
602 beech forests MON and TJN displayed enhanced lagged-effects as a consequence of
603 increasing climate limitation. In contrast, TAN has experienced a shift in the sensitivity
604 to climate around the 1980s which might to be linked to documented regional and global
605 changes in climate. TDH showed a low sensitivity to climate and, despite the large
606 number of studies that have been carried out, it is still rather unclear the role played by
607 land use changes and forest management in the current status of the population.

608 The individual tree approach unveiled that changes in tree sensitivity to climate are
609 consistent within populations and are generally not size-dependent. The general non-size
610 related sensitivity to climate of the peripheral beech populations may be related to a
611 similar canopy status, but further investigations are needed in order to draw confident
612 conclusions.

613

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625

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